

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

POST-HARVEST STORAGE OF APPLE FRUITS OF AZERBAIJANI SELECTION

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Abstract

Currently, apple production in Azerbaijan is growing from year to year, varietal diversity is increasing. For this reason, farmers and people engaged in the production of fruits in agriculture are faced with the task not only to grow fruit, but also to preserve its quality for a long time, without loss. Therefore, at this stage, it is extremely important to conduct scientific research to eliminate existing shortcomings in the field of storage and processing of agricultural products, including apples, in order to obtain scientific results that meet the requirements of a market economy and international standards. This article is just about that.

Keywords: Azerbaijan, apple tree breeding cultivars, post-harvest technologies, cold storage.

1. Introduction

The apple tree has the largest share among the fruit crops grown in the Republic of Azerbaijan.

The fruits of this plant, due to their high nutritional and medicinal value, as well as valuable biological properties, occupy a special place in a healthy diet [1, p. 8; 2, p. 188; 3, p. 205]. They are very valuable raw materials for technological processing into canned food, confectionery and dried fruits [4, p. 270; 5, p. 45].

The high percentage of fruits intended for export led to the need to adapt the post-harvest technology to ensure that the fruits reach the end consumer in optimal condition [6, p. 64].

One of the previous works of the authors of this article was devoted to the study of organoleptic parameters, physical properties and biochemical composition of apple varieties of late introduction [7, p.54].

During storage, the quality of fruits decreases not only due to improper agricultural techniques and untimely harvesting of fruits, but also due to the susceptibility of apples to physiological and fungal diseases due to metabolic disorders, which is affected by this study.

2. Materials and methods

The objects of study were cultivars of breeding of the Research Institute of Fruit and and Tea Industry, such as Sevinj, Vatan, Nasimi, Shabran, Gift to oil workers, Babek, Azerbaijan (originators of the Doctor of Agricultural Sciences Sadikhov A.N., etc.).The following variants of their post-harvest storage were tested:

1. In the conditions of an uncooled warehouse;
2. In the chamber of an ordinary refrigerator;
3. Cold storage in a controlled gas environment.

Before placing the fruits in the refrigerator, a gradual cooling process was carried out at a temperature of +4 ...+6° C for 12 hours.

The shelf life was 150 days.

The chemical composition of the fruits was determined before and after storage.

Temperature and humidity were monitored daily during the entire storage period.

In the chamber of a conventional refrigerator, the temperature during the entire storage period was 1.5 – 2° C, the relative humidity was 90-95%, and in the version with a controlled gas environment, the temperature was 10 C and the relative humidity was 95% with a carbon content (CO₂) of 7%, oxygen (O₂) of 2%.

The natural loss was determined as a percentage based on the difference in the weight of the sample before and after storage .

Diseases were recorded on the basis of visual observations using the atlas of diseases [8, p. 100].

The processing of primary data was carried out using a statistical method, determining the average values of the calculated value based on at least 3-5 repeated definitions [9, p. 20].

3. Theory /calculations

In this study, the emphasis is placed on the comparative study of changes in physical parameters, chemical composition and commodity qualities during the storage of fruits of the above-mentioned cultivars in an uncooled warehouse and during their cold storage in chambers in an unregulated and regulated atmosphere.

4. Results and their discussion

The commercial qualities of apples from proven storage methods are presented in the table.

It shows that at the end of the study, the standard yield of fruits was higher in variants with their storage in the chamber of a conventional refrigerator and in a controlled atmosphere.

Table.

Commercial qualities of apples after storage for 150 days: 1 - in a refrigerated warehouse; 2- in a conventional refrigerator chamber; 3- cold storage in a controlled gas environment, %.

Storage methods	Natural decline	Standard Fruits	Tan	Subcutaneous spotting	Withering	Gleosporous rot	Fruit rot (moniliosis)	Technical decline	Absolute decline
Sevinj									
1	10.9	79.1	0	3.1	9.0	0	4.1	16.2	4.7
2	4.6	92.3	0	2.5	3.2	0	2.0	7.7	0
3	1.0	98.1	1.9	0	0	0	0	1.9	0
Vatan									
1	10.1	78.1	0	2.1	8.9	1.9	3.4	16.3	5.6
2	4.6	93.5	0	2.2	1.3	0	3.0	6.5	0
3	1.0	97.6	0	0	0	1.0	1.4	2.4	0
Nasimi									
1	10.9	76.7	0	5.1	7.9	0	3.3	23.3	7.0
2	6.3	90.1	0	0	0	0	0	9.9	0
3	2.9	96.6	0	0	0	0	0	3.4	0
Babek									
1	10.9	77.8	0	0	0	7.2	9.0	16.2	6.0
2	4.9	91.9	0	2.1	0	2.2	3.8	8.1	0
3	2.2	96.5	0	0	0	1.2	2.3	3.5	0
Gift to oil workers									
1	10.6	79.5	0	0	10.5	0	4.5	15.0	5.5
2	4.6	94.3	0	1.7	2.0	0.3	1.7	5.7	0
3	0.9	98.8	1.2	0	0	0	0	1.2	0
Azerbaijan									
1	10.4	68.9	0	0	14.8	0	8.8	23.6	7.5
2	6.9	90.2	0	0	4.3	0	5.6	9.9	0
3	2.3	96.0	0	0	0	0	0	4.0	0
Shabran									
1	10.4	75.5	0	3.3	10.2	1.7	2.3	17.5	7.0
2	4.5	94.1	0	1.2	2.4	1.3	1.0	5.9	0
3	2.3	97.8	0	0	0	1.0	1.2	2.2	0

The yield of standard fruits in the conditions of a conventional uncooled warehouse by cultivars was 75.5% (Shabran) and 79.5% (A gift to oil workers), after storage in the chamber of a conventional refrigerator, this indicator for the Shabran cultivar increased to 94.1% (Babek cultivar) and 94.3% (the grade is a Gift to oil workers).

The same indicator for the same cultivars in a controlled gas environment was at 97.8% (Shabran) and 98.8% (A gift to oil workers).

The natural decline was highest in the conditions of an uncooled warehouse, especially in the cultivars Vatan (10.1%) and Babek (10.9%).

The natural decrease after storing fruits in the chamber of a conventional refrigerator is much smaller

and amounted to 4.5% for the Shabran cultivar, 4.9% for the Babek cultivar.

The same indicator in the variant with cold storage in a controlled gas environment decreased in the Gift to oilmen cultivar to 0.9%, in the Shabran cultivar to 2.3%.

The physiological diseases during storage included sunburn (Scald), peeling, wilting, microbiological - fruit rot (moniliosis), gleosporous rot.

As can be seen from the same table, in the conditions of an uncooled warehouse, the incidence was the maximum percentage.

In a controlled gas environment, the percentage of technical loss varied from 1.2 (a Gift to oil workers) to 4 (Azerbaijan).

Figure 1. The tan of apples of the cultivar is a Gift to oil workers.

Figure 2. Gloeosporous rot (*Gloeosporium*) in apples of the Babek cultivar.

Despite the fact that the fruits were preserved better in a controlled gas environment, the fruits of some cultivars (Seving, Gift to oil workers) had physiological diseases (Fig.1). Whereas other varieties showed mainly microbiological diseases, such as gloeosporous rot, fruit rot (Fig. 2).

5. Conclusions

From the results obtained, it follows that the fruits of the Sevinj and Gift breeding cultivars to oil workers turned out to be unstable to physiological damage (to sunburn-Scald) in their storage conditions (up to 150 days) in a controlled gas environment with a carbon content (CO₂) - 7%, oxygen (O₂) - 2% at a temperature of 1^o C and a relative humidity of 95%, whereas the fruits of other studied breeding cultivars (Vatan, Nasimi, Shabran, Babek, Azerbaijan) they were deprived of this disadvantage and showed a high yield of standard fruits in the range of 96.5-98.1%.

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